

Comments in response to Knowledge Exchange activity: Alternative Publishing Platforms Scoping paper 2022

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Alternative Publishing Platforms

Toby Steiner 3 years ago

Coming back to my comment from 9months ago, COPIM's Experimental Publishing Compendium has now been made publicly available, and the team will be continuing to curate and develop the database under the remit of the Open Book Futures project (2023-26).

This includes a typology of approaches to Experimental Publishing based on the COPIM WP6 research reports, all of which can be accessed via <https://compendium.copim.ac.uk/> with background details available at <https://compendium.copim.ac.uk/about>

Toby Steiner:

just to add that with Octopus now being hosted by Jisc, this would not fall under the definition of "scholar-led" platforms ;)

Toby Steiner:

Just in case you aren't already aware of this, the 2019 mapping exercise that led to the Mind the Gap report might be a great starting point, see Maxwell, J. W., Hanson, E., Desai, L., Tiampo, C., O'Donnell, K., Ketheeswaran, A., ... Michelle, E. (2019). Mapping the Landscape. In Mind the Gap: A Landscape Analysis of Open Source Publishing Tools and Platforms (1st ed.). <https://doi.org/10.21428/6bc8b38c.2e2f6c3f>

And focusing on open source experimental book publishing, COPIM's Experimental Publishing Compendium might also be of interest here, see <https://compendium.copim.ac.uk/>

Alexandra Howat:

Great paper! One comment is that during your taxonomy work, it might be useful to consider the significance (or not) of the process of peer review and acceptance on an article, and whether this impacts if something is truly considered 'published' or not - is it 'posted' instead? And by extension, are all those discussed therefore publishing platforms? Should this idea be included in the taxonomy? Can be a useful way to relay information about the role of the platform and status of an article.

Secondly - the Microbiology recently launched an open research platform by converting their sound science journal into the open research platform platform using their current technology stack. So this is both not-for-profit led and owned, but underpinned by more traditional/vendor

technologies. So it shows it is possible for smaller orgs can 'stitch' together and create their own and don't have to rely on bigger commercial platforms in the move to open science and innovation. Slightly different angle to the ones discussed in the paper. More info here: <https://microbiologysociety.org/news/society-news/microbiology-society-launches-an-innovative-open-research-platform.html>

Marie-Claude Deboin:

A taxonomy (much more a typology) of publishing platforms seems to be very useful to share concepts, definitions, features. It would be useful to characterize platforms by their owners (public or not), their location, their governance model, the objects that they handle (preprints, postprints, articles, books, research data, ...) and their place in the research life cycle, their software, their functions, their process (depositing, reviewing, editing, publishing, disseminating), their interoperability or interconnections with other platforms or initiatives, their transparency, openness, etc. I think that some institutional or national (public) platforms shouldn't be considered as so traditional as they have integrated in the recent years some innovative, useful and efficient features (I think to OJS with its plug-in for ORCID, Crossref, Dataverse, etc. implemented by many academic institutions)

Toby Steiner:

I do indeed wonder with regards to ambiguities if 'alternative' is a very productive characteristic to work with here - as it quickly raises the question about "an alternative to what exactly"?

I don't think legacy publishers constitute 'platforms' in themselves that one would seek to establish an alternative to - most legacy outlets I'm aware of simply provide paywalled PDF versions of articles on their websites (which hardly makes for an actual "publishing platform" that an alternative to would need to be sought), while a few also provide extended features - that then are suffering from the lock-in effect of paywalls.

So I'm thinking, would the alternative maybe manifest more in the **format of presentation**, i.e. open, often not-for-profit, born-digital, hybrid and multi-format publication platforms that go beyond the 'classic' PDF provision that legacy providers tend to provide?

Jeroen Sondervan:

Dear Tobias,
Many thanks for your comments in the document.

This is a good point and indeed we consider these features on format of presentation as one aspect of 'alternative'. But we think e.g., business models, the disintegration of publishing and innovative strategies to enhance and open the entire research cycle for publication should be taken along in this respect as well.

We acknowledge that it is probably not the most ideal term, but without having a better alternative (no pun intended) yet, we will start with this.

Demmy Verbeke:

I get "publication bias", but what do you mean with "incentive structures"? Is there a platform that explicitly aims to change "incentive structures"? If so, giving the example like in the previous bullets would help.

Toby Steiner:

Just as a formal note, while MIT has been a home to PubPub during its early development phase, I believe the legal entity now maintaining PubPub is the membership organisation Knowledge Futures Group. <https://www.pubpub.org/about>

Jeroen Sondervan:

You are right. We will amend this and acknowledge KFG as hosting service properly (and MIT as early developer).

Toby Steiner:

for open transparency's sake, should this also include a note to point to F1000 being a Taylor & Francis venture? (see Martin Eve's article cited above, and e.g. [Page 2020](#)).

Jeroen Sondervan:

This is already mentioned a few sentences earlier (heading Alternative Publishing Platforms).

Jeroen Sondervan:

Good suggestion to include developments with open books more explicitly. They would fit under the experimental platforms, but also national platforms (like we've been seeing with the development of Finland's open book platform). We will look at your suggestions and try to properly add references and information about the COPIM project and other related initiatives with open books and/or longer formats in the scoping paper.

Toby Steiner:

oh, that'd be great, thanks so much, Jeroen!

+ 1 more...

Toby Steiner:

Not sure if 'stakeholder-governed' is the best way to characterize these platforms? Wouldn't shareholders also be stakeholders in the context of commercial publishers?

Jeroen Sondervan:

Good point. It should be 'academic stakeholder-governed'. We will change this in the next version of this scoping paper.

Toby Steiner:

Would suggest to provide more information on that topic, including references to existing literature in the field, e.g. [Barnes & Gatti, 2019](#) , [Ferwerda & ScholarLed, 2020](#), and [Adema & Moore, 2021](#).

Jeroen Sondervan:

Very good suggestions, we will add these references to a next version of the scoping paper.

d alternative open access publishing platforms has emerged, many of which aim to tackle some of the perceived issues with the journal publishing system other than cost. Platforms represent a move away from the traditional journal as an organising prin

Toby Steiner4 years ago

Thanks so much for your work on this to the whole team involved in this KE initiative!
One conceptual question, if I may - in the opening paragraphs, you mention the breadth of different output channels and formats present in the scholcomm landscape, while the later paras then very much appear to narrow the scope of investigation towards what appears to be a journal-only focus ... Is that the intention of this exercise, or would you see other kinds of platforms also falling under the remit of this scoping exercise?

Toby Steiner4 years ago

Toby Steiner4 years ago

Jeroen Sondervan4 years ago

Yes, and for now these other kinds of platforms would fall under the experimental publishing platforms, where the disintegration of publishing is centric as well as offering other ways of disseminating research outputs in all stages of the research workflow. Examples like the mentioned projects Research Equals, Octopus and even University Journals (despite the name) are non-journal focused publishing platforms.

Toby Steiner3 years ago

Thanks so much for the clarification, Jeroen.
I think why I continue to stumble over this is because all of the mentioned alternative platforms take the conceptual starting point of a STEM-centric focus of what 'research' should look like (aka. the building blocks of a journal), and then work to dissociate these, leading to smaller - still STEM-informed - building blocks (see e.g. Octopus and Research Equals).

What I'm missing in this are examples that would be more relevant to research in the Humanities, while also being more reflective about the mode of production and presentation ... so I'm wondering if it might be an idea - if only for the sake of conceptual breadth of representation - to include more experimental platforms such as Scalar, PubPub and Manifold (to name only three, see the COPIM report mentioned a couple of paragraphs below for more) in the list of platforms mentioned here?

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Dataset: <https://zenodo.org/records/8358919>

Interactive visulisation tool: <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1th-j6gLnNMsQs7mZVFcufOYbPFpdTJwBtD4yzlYiyfE/edit?gid=390320327#gid=390320327>